

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Phylogenetic placement of Planctomycetes (**left panel**) and CPR bacteria (**right panel**) genomes reconstructed in this study (indicated by red dots at branch tips). Scale bar represents the average number of substitutions per site. Black dots at interior nodes indicate ultrafast bootstrap support $\geq 95\%$.

LakeFargette_0920_ALND_PER-ii_52_24_curated

(window = 1000, slide = 10)

Figure S2. Windowed and cumulative GC skew plot for the Peribacteria/PER-ii genome that was curated to completion. The peaked nature of cumulative GC skew, beginning at the origin and proceeding through the terminus, suggests that the genome assembly is accurate (see Chen et al., 2020 doi:10.1101/gr.258640.119).

Figure S3. The newly reconstructed, curated Peribacteria genome (top sequence) is largely syntenous with a reference Peribacteria genome from Rifle, CO. Colored blocks indicate Locally Collinear Blocks as determined by the genome aligner Mauve.

Figure S4. Maximum likelihood (ML) single-protein tree of major capsid protein from putative eukaryotic virus genomes. The tree is rooted between the PAM and the MAPI putative superclades (see: doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912006116).

Figure S5. Maximum likelihood (ML) single-protein tree of VLF3-like protein from putative eukaryotic virus genomes. The tree is rooted between the PAM and the MAPI putative superclades (see: doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912006116).

Figure S6. Transmission electron micrographs of different phenotypes present in starting and final sample after 31 months of incubation. (a-q): starting sample / (A-R): final sample. VLPs: Virus Like Particles. CLPs: Cellular Like Particles. Scale bar: 500 nm (a, l, M, N, R), 200 nm (b, c, e, g-i, m-q, A, G, Q), 100 nm (d, f, j, k, B-F, H-L, O, P).